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TITLE:

Histological examination of mitochondrial morphology in a Parkinson's disease model

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SUMMARY:

In this study we present a method to analyze the morphology of mitochondria based on immunostaining and image analysis *in situ* in mouse brain tissue. We also describe how this tool allow us to detect changes in mitochondrial morphology induced by protein aggregation in models of Parkinson's Disease.

ABSTRACT:

Mitochondria play a central role in the energy metabolism of cells, and their function is especially important for neurons due to their high energetic demand. Therefore, mitochondrial dysfunction is a pathological hallmark of various neurological disorders, including Parkinson's Disease. The shape and organization of the mitochondrial network is highly plastic which allows the cell to respond to environmental cues and needs; in addition, the structure of mitochondria is also tightly linked to their health. Here, we present a protocol to study mitochondrial morphology *in situ*, based on immunostaining of the mitochondrial protein VDAC1 and subsequent image analysis. This tool could be particularly useful for the study of neurodegenerative disorders, as it is able to detect subtle differences in mitochondrial counts and shape induced by aggregates of alpha-synuclein, an aggregation-prone protein heavily involved in the pathology of Parkinson's Disease. This method has allowed us to report that substantia nigra pars compacta dopaminergic neurons harboring pS129 lesions have a reduced Aspect Ratio (AR) compared to their healthy neighboring neurons in a pre-formed fibril intra-cranial injection Parkinson's model.

INTRODUCTION:

The central nervous system has an intense demand for ATP: neurons use ATP to support ionic gradients, neurotransmitter synthesis, synaptic vesicle mobilization, release, and recycling, and to enable local protein translation and degradation. More than 95% of ATP used by the brain is produced by the mitochondria (¹). It is therefore not surprising that mitochondrial dysfunction is particularly harmful for neurons. In fact, mitochondrial function impairments play an important role in several neurological diseases, including neurodegenerative conditions, such as Parkinson's Disease (PD) and Alzheimer's Disease (AD) (^{2, 3}).

Multiple genes unequivocally linked to familiar PD encode proteins that are relevant for mitochondrial function and homeostasis, such as Parkin (^{4, 5, 6}), PTEN-induced kinase 1 (PINK1)

(7, 8) and DJ-1 (9). Further evidence for a role for mitochondrial dysfunction in PD is that treatments with inhibitors of the Complex I of the mitochondrial electron transport chain (Rotenone and MPTP) recapitulate several aspects of PD *in vitro* and *in vivo* (10). However, it is important to state that many pathological processes concur in provoking neuronal loss in PD, together with mitochondrial deficits: oxidative stress, altered calcium homeostasis, failure of the ubiquitin-proteasome and of autophagy-lysosomal systems and protein aggregation are amongst the most studied (reviewed in 11, 12 and 13).

Mitochondria are heterogeneous in their shape: in addition to individual units, they are commonly found as extended reticular and tubular networks. The structure and the cellular location of mitochondria are critical for their function (14); in fact, mitochondrial networks are extremely dynamic, undergoing frequent processes of fission, fusion and mitophagy in order to serve the needs of the cells and to respond to environmental cues (15, 16). In addition, the morphology of mitochondria is intimately linked to their health status. For example, in human optic atrophy, genetic mutations that reduce mitochondrial activity lead to abnormal, slender and hyper-fused mitochondria (17). On the other hand, a variety of human diseases present aberrant mitochondrial morphology, including mitochondrial fragmentation or excessive mitochondrial fusion, which have deleterious effects on mitochondrial function (reviewed in 18). In the context of PD, we as well as others have previously shown that abnormal mitochondrial shape correlates with dysfunction in response to alpha-synuclein aggregates (19). While mitochondrial morphology has been extensively studied *in vitro* both in the context of PD and other diseases (20, 21, 22) protocols for the evaluation of mitochondrial morphology from *in vivo* sections, are lacking. This makes the study of mitochondria *in vivo* in the context of diseases such as PD highly dependent on transgenic animals (23) or the evaluation of midbrain extracts, which cannot provide cellular resolution.

Here, we propose a protocol to study mitochondrial morphology *in situ* as an indicator of their functional status and health, based on immunostaining of the mitochondrial protein VDAC1 (24), followed by image analysis in paraffin-embedded tissue sections. We also show the results of this protocol in *in vitro* and *in vivo* well-characterized PD models: neuroblastoma cells overexpressing *SNCA* and brain tissue from mice subjected to intracranial injection of alpha-synuclein Pre-Formed Fibrils (PFFs). Co-immunostaining with an antibody against alpha-synuclein (in cells) or phosphoSer129-alpha-synuclein (in mouse brains) allowed us to identify the cells with protein aggregate pathology (overexpressed α -synuclein and α -synuclein fibrils, respectively) in our samples, while negative cells served as a non-pathological control within the same samples. Through this analysis we found that cells overexpressing *SNCA* or presenting pS129 lesions have a reduced aspect ratio, indicating fragmentation of mitochondria.

PROTOCOL:

All the procedures described in this section have been performed according to the Ethical framework provided by the University of the Basque Country Reference M20/2022/212, the Government of the Basque Country, the Spanish Government, and the European Union.

Method 1: Mitochondrial morphology analysis by immunofluorescence of *SNCA*-overexpressing

SH-SY5Y cells

Here we briefly describe the generation of the studied *in vitro* material for the study, which will serve as a comparison for the *in situ* obtained results. It is recommended that this type of analysis is performed before launching an *in vivo* experiment for mitochondrial morphology, as it will ensure that all the appropriate imaging and analysis setups are in place.

- 1.1 To increase cellular attachment and facilitate cellular adhesion on flat optical bottom 96 well plates, add 25 μ l/well of coating matrix 1:1000 in DMEM F12 by pipetting. Incubate the plates during 1 h at 37 °C 5 % CO₂.
- 1.2 Count SH-SY5Y using a Neubauer chamber and, after removing the coating matrix by pipetting, seed 10.000 cells/well on the coated 96 well-plate in 50 μ l/well of DMEM F-12 supplemented with 10 % FBS, 2 mM Glutamine and penicillin/streptomycin. Incubate at 37 °C 5 % CO₂.
- 1.3 Prepare for each well a mixture of 250 ng of pcDNA3.1 carrying human wild-type alpha-synuclein, 0.250 μ l of transfection reagent, 0.250 μ l of transfection adjuvant and transfection medium up to 50 μ l. Prepare a master solution with multiples of the indicated volumes according to the number of wells to transfect.
- 1.4 24 h after seeding the cells, remove the culture medium by manual pipetting and pour 50 μ l/well of the solution prepared in step 1.3 by pipetting. Incubate at 37 °C 5 % CO₂.
- 1.5 48 h after transfection, remove the transfection medium by pipetting and fix the cells by pipetting 25 μ l/well of 4 % Paraformaldehyde (PFA) in PBS (CAUTION: paraformaldehyde is a toxic fixative, use appropriate PPE). Incubate during 5 min at R.T.
- 1.6 Remove the fixing solution by pipetting and wash once by pipetting 50 μ l/well of PBS.
- 1.7 After removing the PBS by pipetting, pipet 25 μ l/well of TBS with 0.05 % Tween (TBS-T) and 10 % Normal Donkey Serum (NDS). Incubate during 1 h at R.T. to block unspecific signal.
- 1.8 Prepare a solution of Rabbit-anti- α -synuclein antibody MJFR1 1:1000 and Mouse-anti-TOMM20 antibody 1:100 in TBS-T according to the number of wells to analyse.
- 1.9 Remove the blocking solution by pipetting and pipet 25 μ l/well of primary antibody solution prepared in step 1.8. Incubate overnight at 4 °C.
- 1.10 Remove the primary antibody solution and wash three times by adding and removing 50 μ l/well of TBS-T by pipetting.
- 1.11 Prepare a solution of green secondary antibody anti-Mouse 1:1000 and red secondary antibody key anti-Rabbit 1:1000 in TBS-T according to the number of wells to analyse.

- 1.12 After taking out the PBS of the last wash described in step 1.10 by pipetting, pipet 25 μ l/well of the secondary antibody mixture and incubate the plate during 1 h at R.T.
- 1.13 Remove the secondary antibody solution by pipetting and add 25 μ l/well of DAPI 2 μ g/ml in TBS-T by pipetting. Incubate the plate during 5 min at R.T.
- 1.14 Remove the DAPI solution by using a pipette and wash three times by adding and removing 50 μ l/well of TBS-T with a pipette.
- 1.15 Pipette 80 μ l/well of PBS with 0.02 % sodium azide (CAUTION: sodium azide is toxic, use appropriate PPE) and store the plate at 4 °C.
- 1.16 Take pictures by high-content automated fluorescence microscope or equivalent confocal imaging system equipped with a 60x objective.
- 1.17 Perform analysis of the TOMM20 signal of single cells (avoid any cells displaying nuclei undergoing apoptosis, necrosis or mitosis) by using Fiji: first, select and isolate the Region of Interest (ROI) by drawing around the positive or negative cell (as appropriate) and using the “Crop” function. Select the ROI by using a channel with cellular autofluorescence or a marker unrelated to the analysis in order to avoid bias in the selection of the ROI. OPTIONAL: if the image is excessively pixelated use the “Smooth” function to obtain higher edge definition. Should the smooth function be applied to an image, please apply to all subsequent images.
- 1.18 Then, use the “Convolve” function (Kernel mode, in Process > Filters) to reduce the background. NOTE: this is optional and usually not necessary in 5 μ m tissue sections due to the thinner nature of the sections.
- 1.19 Activate the “Shape description” and “Limit to threshold” options on the “Set measurement” function (make sure these are activated through the analysis).
- 1.20 In the “Adjust” menu, select the “Threshold” function, and adjust the threshold level. The threshold settings must be maintained for all the cells of the same sample. Ensure you adequately visualize the mitochondrial network as shown in the representative images of this article, while discarding background pixels.
- 1.21 Use the “Analyse particles” tool on the Analyse tab. Set an appropriate size to capture the mitochondria, in this example we used size “3-Infinity”, activate “Pixel units” and select “Show: Masks” in order to visualize the result. Fiji will calculate the counts and other shape parameters.
- 1.22 Perform statistical analysis of the data as appropriate. In our case we used T-Test to analyse the Aspect ratio (AR) and Counts after normality testing with the D’Agostino and Pearson

normality tests.

Method 2: Generation of PFFs and PFF intra-cranial injections in mice

Here we briefly describe the generation of the studied *in situ* material for the study and the intracranial injection process. This protocol is adapted from Luk et al. (25).

- 2.1 In order to obtain PFFs, α -Syn (5 mg/ml; Peptide) was shaken at 37 °C and 250 r.p.m. for 7 days to induce aggregation of α -synuclein.
- 2.2 Fibrils were then sonicated at 20 % amplitude and 0.25 cycle duty until optimal fragmentation was achieved and observed by negative stain of the samples and transmission electron microscopy.
- 2.3 To prepare male and female wild-type C57Bl/6 mice (3 months old) for striatal PFF injections, administer Meloxicam/Metacam (5 mg/kg) in saline solution via intraperitoneal injection and 1 ml of sterile saline solution via two 0.5 ml intradermal injection.
- 2.4 Induce aesthesia with 4 % Isoflurane and 0.7 % O₂ in induction chamber. Shave the upper part of mouse head and gently insert the animal into the frame of the stereotactic apparatus on a heat block.
- 2.5 Maintain the anaesthetic plan by giving the animal inhalation anaesthesia (1-2 % Isoflurane in 0.7 % O₂) through a nose mask during the whole injection process.
- 2.6 After cutting the skin to expose the skull and appropriate disinfection of the wound, identify the following coordinates from Bregma: - 0.5 mm anteroposterior, +/- 2.5 mm mediolateral and drill there a 0.5 mm diameter hole into the skull to expose the brain surface.
- 2.7 Inject 1.5 μ l of PFFs by stereotactic delivery to the coordinates indicated in step 2.6 from Bregma and - 2.7 mm dorsoventral (from top brain) at a flow rate of 100 nl/min with a 32-gauge Hamilton syringe. Withdrawn the syringe 5 min post injection.
- 2.8 Suture the wound (single surgeon stitches with 2 double knots and then a single knot), stop anaesthetic inhalation, remove the mouse from frame and let it recover in an appropriate recovery cage before returning it to the home cage.
- 2.9 Three months later, give the mouse 300 μ l of 200 mg/ml Sodium Pentobarbital in saline solution via intraperitoneal injection. Once pain reflex is lost, make an incision on the chest, lift the ribs to expose the heart and transcardially perfuse with a 10 ml of PBS and 35 ml of 4 % Paraformaldehyde in PBS by using a 50 ml syringe connected to a 23 G butterfly needle.
- 2.10 Remove the brain and post-fix in 4 % PFA for 24 h at 4 °C, then remove the PFA solution and store in 70 % ethanol at 4 °C.

- 2.11 Put the brain into appropriate plastic embedding boxes and incubate in 95 % ethanol during one hour at R.T. Replace the embedding reagent and incubate again for 1 h.
- 2.12 Put the brain into appropriate plastic embedding boxes and incubate in 100 % ethanol during 1 h at R.T. Replace the embedding reagent and incubate again for 1 h.
- 2.13 Put the brain into appropriate plastic embedding boxes and incubate in Xylene or Xylene-substitute during 1 h at R.T. Replace the embedding reagent and incubate again for 1 h.
- 2.14 Remove the Xylene or Xylene-substitute and incubate the sample in warm paraffin for 1 h. Replace the paraffin and incubate for one additional hour.
- 2.15 Mount the brain on the embedding boxes with warm paraffin and let it dry overnight. Cut 5 μm sections by microtome and mount them on glass slides.

Method 3: Mitochondrial morphology analysis by immunohistochemistry on paraffin-embedded brain slices from PFF-injected mice

- 3.1 Dewax: this step is necessary to remove the paraffin and enable the rehydration of the samples. Dip the slides ten times in Xylene substitute and incubate the slides during 2 min in Xylene substitute. Dip again ten times in Xylene substitute before taking out the samples from Xylene substitute.
- 3.2 Rehydration: repeat the procedure described in step 3.1 with the following solutions: 100 % EtOH, 95 % EtOH, 70 % EtOH, and twice with ddH₂O.
- 3.3 Antigen retrieval and immunostaining: start by transferring the samples to a microwavable container with ddH₂O.
- 3.4 Warm up 100 x citrate buffer pH 6 stored at 4°C (detergents may have precipitated) and prepare 350 ml of fresh 1 x citrate buffer. Pour citrate buffer into a convenient plastic container with lid.
- 3.5 Put the slides into the citrate buffer container (CRITICAL: check they always stay beneath the level of the buffer) and put the lid on (CAUTION: ensure the lid is NOT completely closed otherwise the container may burst in the microwave).
- 3.6 Microwave at 700 W: 4 min + 5 min rest, 1.5 min + 5 min rest. Top-up citrate buffer and microwave again 1.5 min + 5 min rest, 1.5 min + 5 min rest, 1.5 min + 5min rest.
- 3.7 Cool down the samples in citrate buffer on ice during 20 min. Wash the sample with ddH₂O. NOTE: antigen retrieval may vary according to specific antibody requirements.

- 3.8 Dry the samples slides by using a paper towel, without touching the tissue. Draw rectangles with pap-pen around the pieces of tissue.
- 3.9 Transfer all the slides to a slide immune-staining box and wash gently a couple of times with TBS + 0.05 % TWEEN (TBS-T). Check TBS-T drops stays inside the pap-pen rectangles.
- 3.10 Remove TBS-T from the samples by tapping on a paper towel. Gently pour 50 μ l of blocking solution (10 % NDS in TBS-T) into each rectangle (without touching the tissue) and incubate for 1h at RT. NOTE: volumes may vary according to the size of the tissue, try to ensure that:
i) the pap-penned area is similar across samples, and that ii) the area is fully covered by the chosen buffer volume.
- 3.11 Remove the blocking solution from the samples by tapping on a paper towel. Gently pour by pipetting 50 μ l/rectangle of the following primary antibody mixture in TBS-T: anti-Tyrosine Hydroxylase 1:250, anti-VDAC1 1:100 and anti-pSer129 α -synuclein EP1536Y 1:2000.
- 3.12 Incubate overnight at 4 °C.
- 3.13 Wash by pipetting TBS-T on the slides and remove it by tapping on paper towel. Repeat three times.
- 3.14 Add by pipetting 50 μ l/rectangle of secondary antibody mixture: green secondary anti-Chicken, red secondary anti-Mouse and far red secondary anti-Rabbit 1:1000 in TBS-T. Incubate at 37 °C during 1 h in the dark.
- 3.15 Wash three times with TBS-T as described in step 3.13.
- 3.16 Incubate with DAPI 2 μ g/ml in TBS-T during 1 min. Remove DAPI solution by tapping on paper towel. Wash three times with TBS-T as described at step 3.13.
- 3.17 Mount a glass cover-slide on the samples by using drops/slide of mounting reagent. Gently press to eliminate bubbles and let the samples dry during 1 h at R.T. Afterwards, store at 4 °C in the dark.
- 3.18 Image at least 50 cells in different fields by using a structured illumination fluorescence imaging system equipped with 60x oil objective or confocal technology.
- 3.19 Perform analysis of the VDAC1 signal of single cells by using Fiji as indicated above. For this specific set of images, we applied a smooth filter and set the particle size as “25-infinity” on the “Analyse Particles” function from the “Analyse” menu.
- 3.20 Perform appropriate statistical test for your resulting analysis.

REPRESENTATIVE RESULTS:

In order to ensure that the appropriate imaging and analysis conditions are in place for the *in situ* evaluation of mitochondrial morphology in tissue, an *in vitro* exploration of mitochondrial morphology in response to a known modulator of mitochondrial morphology is recommended (Protocol 1). As an example, we genetically overexpressed SNCA in SH-SY5Y cells in order to induce changes in mitochondrial morphology as previously described (²⁶). Other examples that could be used as a control to worsen mitochondria morphology would be starvation, or the use of mitochondrial activity inhibitors such as MPP+. Cells were transfected and stained for alpha-synuclein (AS) so as to separate SNCA+ (AS+) and SNCA- (AS-) cells. They were also stained for TOMM20 (²⁷) to visualize the mitochondrial network of the cells. In order to make this analysis as similar as possible to that of a 5 µm tissue section, one confocal plane was analyzed as opposed to a maximum projection of multiple planes. Morphological analysis of one confocal plane of TOMM20 revealed that both the total number of mitochondria and their aspect ratio or AR (which correlates with the elongation of the organelle) were reduced in response to SNCA overexpression (Fig. 1).

We performed immunostaining for the mitochondrial protein VDAC1 in 5 µm paraffin-embedded mouse brain sections from animals injected with PFFs as described in the protocol section above. Substantia nigra pars compacta (SNc) dopaminergic neurons, which undergo degeneration in PD, were revealed through co-immunostaining with anti-Tyrosine Hydroxylase (TH) and were regionally separated from the ventral tegmental area and the substantia nigra pars lateralis. On the other hand, anti-phosphoSer129- α -synuclein (pS129) staining allowed us to discriminate cells that harbored pS129 lesions from healthy cells (pS129+ versus pS129-). SNc images of three different animals were taken and subsequent image analysis of VDAC1 staining of TH-positive neurons revealed a reduction of both mitochondrial number counts and aspect ratio between neurons bearing pS129 lesions and neurons lacking these (Fig. 2). These results indicate that the mitochondrial morphology of neurons harboring pS129 lesions is impaired in comparison to that of cells lacking pS129 lesions.

While this particular experiment shows a reduction in the AR thereby highlighting a reduction in the elongation of mitochondrial together with a reduction in global counts, indicating a worsening of the mitochondrial morphology, it is important to note that the interpretation of the data should be experiment dependent. For example, a reduction in AR and counts can point to a global reduction in mitochondrial content as well as fragmentation, while a reduction in AR but an increase in global counts would point to a mitochondrial fragmentation phenotype. Therefore, it is important to interpret the data in the context of both measures.

FIGURE AND TABLE LEGENDS:

Figure 1: Mitochondrial morphology in a SNCA-overexpressing *in vitro* model. Co-immunostaining for TOMM20 (green), α -synuclein (AS, red) and DAPI (blue) on SNCA-overexpressing and not overexpressing (AS+ and AS-, respectively) cells (A). Detail of a AS- cell (B), and of a AS+ cell (C). Black and white images in panels B and C represent the masks of the TOMM20 signal after applying the Fiji function described in the Protocol section. This mask enables the quantification of the shape of the resulting structures. Mitochondrial counts and Aspect Ratio (AR) values of AS- and AS+ cells (N=25 cells per condition) were quantified and represented as individual values as

well as average \pm SEM; ** p-value < 0.05 T-Test (D). Normality was assessed through D'Agostino and Pearson normality test.

Figure 2: Mitochondrial morphology is affected in neurons harboring pS129 lesions. Co-immunostaining for TH (green), VDAC1 (red), phosphoS129- α -synuclein (purple) and DAPI (blue) of the SNc of PFF-injected mice (A). Detail of a phosphoS129- α -synuclein-negative (pS129-) dopaminergic neuron (B), and of a phosphoS129- α -synuclein-positive (pS129+) dopaminergic neuron (C). Black and white images in panels B and C represent the masks of the TOMM20 signal after applying the Fiji function described in the Protocol section. This mask enables the quantification of the shape of the resulting structures. Negative and positive cells were counted in samples from three different animals, as illustrated by the different colors of the individual graphed values (blue, green and orange). Mitochondrial counts and AR quantification of pS129- (N=29) versus pS129+ (N=22) in dopaminergic neurons was represented as average \pm SEM as well as individual cell values; ** p-value < 0.05 T-Test (D). Normality was assessed through D'Agostino and Pearson normality test.

TABLE OF MATERIALS:

DISCUSSION:

Overall, this study shows that immuno-staining combined with image analysis is a reliable method for analysing mitochondrial morphology. In fact, it allows to quantify the amount of mitochondria, as well as some morphological parameters, such as the aspect ratio, in both cell culture and tissue. The amount of mitochondria is directly linked to the functional status of the fission and fusion mechanisms of the samples, whereas the AR value relies on the elongation of the organelle. This method may be particularly valuable for the quick evaluation of the mitochondrial abnormalities in models of PD, in which altered mitochondrial morphology, dynamics and functions are well-known pathological mechanisms (28, 29). Alpha-synuclein also plays a relevant role in PD: indeed, alpha-synuclein is one of the components of Lewy Bodies, the cytoplasmatic fibrillary aggregates that are used for post-mortem diagnosis of PD patients (30). Moreover, mutations in the SNCA gene were found in patients with both familiar and sporadic PD (reviewed in 31). phosphorylation of alpha-synuclein at Ser129 has extensively been shown to label Lewy-Body-like pathology, which emerges after PFF insult and elicits various toxic effects (32, 26).

By using the tool presented here, we were able to count less mitochondria and we observed altered mitochondrial AR values in the presence of both overexpressed and aggregated alpha-synuclein (cells with α -synuclein-staining and neurons bearing phosphoSer129 α -synuclein-positive lesions, respectively), compared to cells lacking such lesions (α -synuclein- and phosphoS129 α -synuclein-negative cells). These results are in agreement with previous reports showing how direct alpha-synuclein-mitochondria interactions result in toxic effects on mitochondrial function and homeostasis in PD (26, 33 and 34). Indeed, it was reported that mice with α -synuclein mutations exhibit increased mitochondrial DNA damage (35) and mitophagy (36, 37). Moreover, it was described that increased α -synuclein levels promote mitochondrial fission/fragmentation, induce reactive oxygen species within mitochondria and dysregulate mitochondrial protein expression in cell lines and mouse models overexpressing α -synuclein (38,

³⁹ and ²⁶).

It is important to highlight that this tool highly depends on the antibodies used for the study; careful morphological evaluation of the antibody stain used is imperative in order to detect the appropriate subcellular compartment. As this technique is based on 5 µm sections and therefore will use single focal planes for the analysis of the mitochondrial structures, it is important to note that the absence of a phenotype will not rule out the existence of a phenotype, as it is possible that subtle differences in mitochondrial morphology may not be detected by this method.

While us and others have previously used similar approaches to evaluate mitochondrial morphology *in vivo* (⁴⁰), there is a need for a detailed protocol to be made accessible to the research community for this assessment. The significance of this study is that it is possible to apply this method to a wide range of *in vivo* disease models for the assessment of mitochondrial morphological abnormalities and the identification of the potential pathology, which may eventually facilitate the screening of lead compounds for the treatment of such disorders. While this analysis is currently limited to paraffin-embedded tissue, the advantage of the method is that it can be applied to any disease model after terminal tissue collection, making it a very versatile tool.

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DISCLOSURES:

We wish to report no conflict of interests.

REFERENCES:

1. Yang, Y., Lu, B. Mitochondrial Morphogenesis, Distribution, and Parkinson Disease. *Journal of Neuropathology and Experimental Neurology*. **68** (9), 953–963, doi: 10.1097/NEN.0b013e3181b2048c (2009).
2. Schapira, A.H. Mitochondria in the aetiology and pathogenesis of Parkinson's disease. *The Lancet Neurology*. **7** (1), 97–109, doi: 10.1016/S1474-4422(07)70327-7 (2008).
3. Swerdlow, R.H. Mitochondria and Mitochondrial Cascades in Alzheimer's Disease. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*. **62** (3), 1403–1416, doi: 10.3233/JAD-170585 (2018).
4. Hedrich, K. *et al.* Distribution, type, and origin of Parkin mutations: Review and case studies. *Movement Disorders*. **19** (10), 1146–1157, doi: 10.1002/mds.20234 (2004).
5. Kahle, P.J., Haass, C. How does parkin ligate ubiquitin to Parkinson's disease? *EMBO reports*. **5** (7), 681–685, doi: 10.1038/sj.embor.7400188 (2004).
6. Dawson, T.M., Dawson, V.L. The role of parkin in familial and sporadic Parkinson's disease. *Movement Disorders*. **25** (S1), S32–S39, doi: 10.1002/mds.22798 (2010).
7. Pickrell, A.M., Youle, R.J. The Roles of PINK1, Parkin, and Mitochondrial Fidelity in Parkinson's Disease. *Neuron*. **85** (2), 257–273, doi: 10.1016/j.neuron.2014.12.007 (2015).
8. Zhi, L. *et al.* Loss of PINK1 causes age-dependent decrease of dopamine release and mitochondrial dysfunction. *Neurobiology of Aging*. **75**, 1–10, doi: 10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2018.10.025 (2019).

9. Bonifati, V. *et al.* DJ-1 (PARK7), a novel gene for autosomal recessive, early onset parkinsonism. *Neurological Sciences*. **24** (3), 159–160, doi: 10.1007/s10072-003-0108-0 (2003).
10. Chia, S.J., Tan, E.-K., Chao, Y.-X. Historical Perspective: Models of Parkinson’s Disease. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. **21** (7), 2464, doi: 10.3390/ijms21072464 (2020).
11. Wilson, D.M., Cookson, M.R., Van Den Bosch, L., Zetterberg, H., Holtzman, D.M., Dewachter, I. Hallmarks of neurodegenerative diseases. *Cell*. **186** (4), 693–714, doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2022.12.032 (2023).
12. Moore, D.J., West, A.B., Dawson, V.L., Dawson, T.M. MOLECULAR PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF PARKINSON’S DISEASE. *Annual Review of Neuroscience*. **28** (1), 57–87, doi: 10.1146/annurev.neuro.28.061604.135718 (2005).
13. Olanow, C.W., Tatton, W.G. ETIOLOGY AND PATHOGENESIS OF PARKINSON’S DISEASE. *Annual Review of Neuroscience*. **22** (1), 123–144, doi: 10.1146/annurev.neuro.22.1.123 (1999).
14. Nunnari, J., Suomalainen, A. Mitochondria: In Sickness and in Health. *Cell*. **148** (6), 1145–1159, doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2012.02.035 (2012).
15. Okamoto, K., Shaw, J.M. Mitochondrial Morphology and Dynamics in Yeast and Multicellular Eukaryotes. *Annual Review of Genetics*. **39** (1), 503–536, doi: 10.1146/annurev.genet.38.072902.093019 (2005).
16. Malpartida, A.B., Williamson, M., Narendra, D.P., Wade-Martins, R., Ryan, B.J. Mitochondrial Dysfunction and Mitophagy in Parkinson’s Disease: From Mechanism to Therapy. *Trends in Biochemical Sciences*. **46** (4), 329–343, doi: 10.1016/j.tibs.2020.11.007 (2021).
17. Zou, W. *et al.* Nanoscopic quantification of sub-mitochondrial morphology, mitophagy and mitochondrial dynamics in living cells derived from patients with mitochondrial diseases. *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*. **19** (1), 136, doi: 10.1186/s12951-021-00882-9 (2021).
18. Navaratnarajah, T., Anand, R., Reichert, A.S., Distelmaier, F. The relevance of mitochondrial morphology for human disease. *The International Journal of Biochemistry & Cell Biology*. **134**, 105951, doi: 10.1016/j.biocel.2021.105951 (2021).
19. Zambon, F. *et al.* Cellular α -synuclein pathology is associated with bioenergetic dysfunction in Parkinson’s iPSC-derived dopamine neurons. *Human Molecular Genetics*. **28** (12), 2001–2013, doi: 10.1093/hmg/ddz038 (2019).
20. Cherubini, M., Lopez-Molina, L., Gines, S. Mitochondrial fission in Huntington’s disease mouse striatum disrupts ER-mitochondria contacts leading to disturbances in Ca²⁺ efflux and Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) homeostasis. *Neurobiology of Disease*. **136**, 104741, doi: 10.1016/j.nbd.2020.104741 (2020).
21. Parihar, M.S., Parihar, A., Fujita, M., Hashimoto, M., Ghafourifar, P. Alpha-synuclein overexpression and aggregation exacerbates impairment of mitochondrial functions by augmenting oxidative stress in human neuroblastoma cells. *The International Journal of Biochemistry & Cell Biology*. **41** (10), 2015–2024, doi: 10.1016/j.biocel.2009.05.008 (2009).
22. Wiemerslage, L., Lee, D. Quantification of mitochondrial morphology in neurites of dopaminergic neurons using multiple parameters. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods*. **262**, 56–65, doi: 10.1016/j.jneumeth.2016.01.008 (2016).
23. Liu, Y.-T. *et al.* Mt-Keima detects PINK1-PRKN mitophagy *in vivo* with greater sensitivity than mito-QC. *Autophagy*. **17** (11), 3753–3762, doi: 10.1080/15548627.2021.1896924 (2021).
24. Shoshan-Barmatz, V., Shteinfer-Kuzmine, A., Verma, A. VDAC1 at the Intersection of Cell Metabolism, Apoptosis, and Diseases. *Biomolecules*. **10** (11), 1485, doi: 10.3390/biom10111485

- (2020).
25. Luk, K.C. *et al.* Pathological α -Synuclein Transmission Initiates Parkinson-like Neurodegeneration in Nontransgenic Mice. *Science*. **338** (6109), 949–953, doi: 10.1126/science.1227157 (2012).
 26. Ryan, B.J. *et al.* REST Protects Dopaminergic Neurons from Mitochondrial and α -Synuclein Oligomer Pathology in an Alpha Synuclein Overexpressing BAC-Transgenic Mouse Model. *The Journal of Neuroscience*. **41** (16), 3731–3746, doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1478-20.2021 (2021).
 27. Yamamoto, H. *et al.* Dual role of the receptor Tom20 in specificity and efficiency of protein import into mitochondria. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. **108** (1), 91–96, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1014918108 (2011).
 28. Exner, N., Lutz, A.K., Haass, C., Winklhofer, K.F. Mitochondrial dysfunction in Parkinson's disease: molecular mechanisms and pathophysiological consequences. *The EMBO Journal*. **31** (14), 3038–3062, doi: 10.1038/emboj.2012.170 (2012).
 29. Grünewald, A., Kumar, K.R., Sue, C.M. New insights into the complex role of mitochondria in Parkinson's disease. *Progress in Neurobiology*. **177**, 73–93, doi: 10.1016/j.pneurobio.2018.09.003 (2019).
 30. Baba, M. *et al.* Aggregation of alpha-synuclein in Lewy bodies of sporadic Parkinson's disease and dementia with Lewy bodies. *The American journal of pathology*. **152** (4), 879–84 (1998).
 31. Vázquez-Vélez, G.E., Zoghbi, H.Y. Parkinson's Disease Genetics and Pathophysiology. *Annual Review of Neuroscience*. **44** (1), 87–108, doi: 10.1146/annurev-neuro-100720-034518 (2021).
 32. Mahul-Mellier, A.-L. *et al.* The process of Lewy body formation, rather than simply α -synuclein fibrillization, is one of the major drivers of neurodegeneration. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. **117** (9), 4971–4982, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1913904117 (2020).
 33. Ganguly, U. *et al.* Interaction of α -synuclein and Parkin in iron toxicity on SH-SY5Y cells: implications in the pathogenesis of Parkinson's disease. *Biochemical Journal*. **477** (6), 1109–1122, doi: 10.1042/BCJ20190676 (2020).
 34. Ganjam, G.K. *et al.* Mitochondrial damage by α -synuclein causes cell death in human dopaminergic neurons. *Cell Death & Disease*. **10** (11), 865, doi: 10.1038/s41419-019-2091-2 (2019).
 35. Martin, L.J. *et al.* Parkinson's Disease α -Synuclein Transgenic Mice Develop Neuronal Mitochondrial Degeneration and Cell Death. *The Journal of Neuroscience*. **26** (1), 41–50, doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.4308-05.2006 (2006).
 36. Choubey, V. *et al.* Mutant A53T α -Synuclein Induces Neuronal Death by Increasing Mitochondrial Autophagy. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. **286** (12), 10814–10824, doi: 10.1074/jbc.M110.132514 (2011).
 37. Chen, L., Xie, Z., Turkson, S., Zhuang, X. A53T Human α -Synuclein Overexpression in Transgenic Mice Induces Pervasive Mitochondria Macroautophagy Defects Preceding Dopamine Neuron Degeneration. *The Journal of Neuroscience*. **35** (3), 890–905, doi: 10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0089-14.2015 (2015).
 38. Kamp, F. *et al.* Inhibition of mitochondrial fusion by α -synuclein is rescued by PINK1, Parkin and DJ-1. *The EMBO Journal*. **29** (20), 3571–3589, doi: 10.1038/emboj.2010.223 (2010).
 39. Nakamura, K. *et al.* Direct Membrane Association Drives Mitochondrial Fission by the Parkinson Disease-associated Protein α -Synuclein. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. **286** (23), 20710–20726, doi: 10.1074/jbc.M110.213538 (2011).
 40. Park, J. *et al.* Abnormal Mitochondria in a Non-human Primate Model of MPTP-induced

Parkinson's Disease: Drp1 and CDK5/p25 Signaling. *Experimental Neurobiology*. **28** (3), 414–424, doi: 10.5607/en.2019.28.3.414 (2019).

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

Table 1

Name of Material/ Equipment	Company	Catalog Number	Comments/Description
Alexa fluor 488/594-Donkey anti-Mouse	Invitrogen	A21202; A21203	green/red dye-Donkey anti-Mouse
Alexa fluor 594/647-Donkey anti-Rabbit	Invitrogen	A21207 A31573	red/far red dye-Donkey anti-Rabbit
AlexaFluor 488-Donkey anti-Chicken	Jackson ImmunoResearch	703-545-155	green dye-Donkey anti-Chicken
Anti- α -synuclein antibody MJFR1 (Rabbit)	Abcam	ab138501	
Anti-P ^{Ser129} α -synuclein EP1536Y (Rabbit) antibody	Abcam	ab51253	
Anti-Tyrosine Hydroxylase (Chicken) antibody	Abcam	ab76442	
Anti-TOM 20 (Mouse) antibody	Santa Cruz	sc-17764	
Anti-VDAC1 (Mouse) antibody	Santa Cruz	sc-390996	
Citrate buffer 100X stock: 120mM citrate buffer, 5% Tween in water (pH 6)	Home-made		
EVOS M7000 Imaging System	ThermoFisher Scientific		High-content automated fluorescence microscope
4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindol, dihydrochloruro (DAPI)	Invitrogen	D1306	
D-MEM F12	Gibco	A321331020	
Fetal Bovine Serum	Gibco	10270106	
Flat optical bottom 96 well plates	Greiner	675090	
FluorSave Reagent	Millipore	345789-20ML	Mounting reagent
Glutamine 200mM	Gibco	25030-024	
32-gauge Hamilton syringe	Hamilton	7632-01	
Lipofectamine and Plus Reagent	Invitrogen	11668-019; 11514-015	Transfection reagent and transfection adjuvant
Matrigel	Corning	354230	Coating matrix
Microtome	ThermoFisher Scientific		
Normal Donkey Serum	Gibco	PCN5000	
ImmEdge Hydrophobic Barrier Pen	Vector Laboratories	H-4000	PAP-pen
Penicillin/Streptomycin solution	Gibco	15140-122	
Opti-MEM	Gibco	31985070	Transfection medium
PCDNA4 plasmid (backbone)	Addgene	41036	
SH-SY5Y cells/well	ATCC	HTB-11	
Xylene substitute	Labbox	22L36504	
Zeiss Axio Imager Apotome 2	Carl Zeiss		Structured illumination fluorescence imaging system